

A NON-PROFIT ONLINE MARKETPLACE PLATFORM OF TRAVEL AGENCIES IN TURKEY: TURSAB ROTA

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Abstract

Travel and tourism industry have been inevitably affected by the information and communication technologies. Almost all the components in this industry have experienced some serious changes, transformations and impacts. These alterations bring together some opportunities and challenges in its very nature. Consumer demand and consumer behaviour have also been subject to change. That's why new online e-commerce applications and new business models came into the scene. Business to Business (B2B) sales platforms are one of the examples of this change. There exist some studies about the private sector profit oriented B2Bs in the literature. Nevertheless, there is no example in the field of non-profit basis associations. The basic objective of the current study is to introduce such an example in Turkey founded by TURSAB (Association of Turkish Travel Agencies). The legal fundamentals of TURSAB, the foundation process of Rota platform, the contents of Rota and the member travel agencies' website integration types were examined in accordance with this purpose. The introductory texts and data of this preliminary research were provided from the team members working for Rota platform. The estimations of these team members are mainly the internationalization of the platform in due course and the extension of authentic tours.

Keywords: Package Tours, Travel Agencies, TURSAB, B2B Marketplace

JEL Code: M20, M30, L83

1. Introduction

Tourism is a considerable global economic force which operates through the consumers' information search and decision-making processes. Recently, these processes have increasingly taken place online. Various technological platforms have reshaped the landscape and distribution of tourism information for both larger companies and small and medium sized enterprises (Mitas et al., 2015). Travel technology (also called tourism technology, and hospitality automation) is the

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application of Information Technology (IT) or Information and Communications Technology (ICT) in the travel, tourism and hospitality industry (Olya, 2020). The staggering developments in ICTs have also altered the conventional know how of tourism. Hotels, tour operators, travel agencies as the dominant components of tourism industry have got their share from this inevitable change. Because the conventional demand and marketing styles have become old-fashioned, such a transformation is to be realized by the industry.

As vacation time is limited and tourism is a costly activity, tourists wish to make the most of their stay. There is an industry around travel guides, maps and advice. This business is also being explored on the Internet and is now making its way to the ubiquitous smartphone, where it can take advantage of interactivity, positioning systems, wireless Internet access, augmented reality, social networks and crowd sourcing. However, often the foundation for tourism applications continues to be accurate, high quality, reliable information from authoritative sources (Pereira et al. 2015).

New generations and new consumers enforced the firms to be in online sales platforms. Mostly, travel agencies experienced this change. Appearance of online travel agencies (OTAs) and online sales platforms are some instances of such a change. Using the Internet as a means of communication with the consumers and as a marketing activity seems to be the most considerable reason for using the Internet (Kozak, 2007). Web portals therefore are the technology of choice for Online Travel Agents (OTA) to seamlessly combine own IBEs/WBEs (Internet booking engines/Web booking engines) with those of third-party providers of flight, hotel, rental car, and touristic booking engines or dynamic packaging engines to aggregate bookable offers of many market suppliers (Goecke, 2020).

Internet Booking Engine (IBE) is a kind of an application utilized online. That's because it is also named as Web Booking Engine / Online Booking Engine (WBE / OBE). This application provides the booking of any sort of travel on the internet. Rates of the travel firms and the allocated amounts can be listed spontaneously. In this manner, it presents a real time confirmation. This confirmation is easily displayed to the consumer of the travel service. The travel product itself may also be displayed in detail. Such applications might be independent and single (hotel rooms sales in a hotel website). In these circumstances, the IBE is frequently connected directly to the Central Reservation System (CRS) or Property Management System (PMS). On the other hand, they might be seen in the combination of more than one service. These services might be exemplified as hotels, flights and rental cars. Moreover, they might be integrated from a third-party vendor into the website (<https://www.h2c.de/glossary/#I-ibe-internet-booking-engine>).

There exists an enormous amount of direct online sales and various means for such sales. Moreover, tourism operations also use some online platforms while creating some e-commerce among each other. In these circumstances, business to business (B2B) sales platforms are very useful and utilized by many commercial firms. Nevertheless, the professional associations of travel agencies do not have

such an organisation of creating an online platform to reinforce the power of supply. By this way, the authenticity of the tour would be far more considerable than the size of the travel agency which presents that tour. Hence, the small sized travel agencies will have the equal sales opportunities in an online platform by using the recognisability of the larger sized travel agencies or tour operators. In this study, as the first example among the national associations of travel agencies' B2B operations, TURSAB created Rota platform of a national online B2B marketplace like the profit-oriented examples of both national and international commercial firms. In order to understand the origin of the idea, the legal aspects which allow TURSAB to realize this project should be examined briefly.

2. Legal Foundation of TURSAB

The Law Concerning Travel Agencies and the Association of Travel Agencies went in effect on 28th September 1972 (Law No.1618). The Law is consisted of three sections.

Section One: Travel Agencies

This section contains articles concerning procedures and provisions set for the establishment, trade name of the enterprise, branch offices, operation of travel agencies, permissions, grouping, operation certificates, qualifications of the travel agency owner, the manager in charge, travel agency personnel; travel agency offices, security to be received from the travel agencies, obligations of travel agencies, credit and other facilities provided to, inspection and supervision, cancellation and penalties.

Section Two: The Association of Travel Agencies

This section contains articles under the headings; aim and the establishment, duties of the association, bodies of the association, and revenue of the association. Subsections contain articles concerning general assembly, executive board, disciplinary council and the inspection Council, Election, establishment of the bodies and their duties.

Revenue of the Association

According to Article 35 of the Law, the revenue of the Association of Turkish Travel Agencies, shall consist of the following sources: Registration fees to the association and membership fees, revenue to be obtained from the courses and seminars organized for training the travel agency personnel, donations and contributions.

Section Three

This section includes final provisions, interim articles and article concerning execution of the Law.

Regulations Relevant to Law No.1618

Regulation Pertaining to Travel Agencies

This Regulation was prepared and has been put into effect in accordance with the Law Concerning Travel Agencies and Association of Travel Agencies, No 1618. The Regulation covers the principles, the procedures related to the implementation of the provisions applicable to travel agencies under Law.1618, concerning the establishment and operation of travel agencies, scope of travel agency services qualifications required for the owners, managers in charge, personnel, and work place etc. This regulation contains seven sections, under the following headings:

- General Provisions
- Services and Groups of Travel Agencies and Principles of Operation (Article 4 of this section specifies exclusive services to travel agencies)
- Establishment, Characteristics and Inspection of Travel Agencies
- Qualifications of the Travel Agency Services
- Consumer Rights
- Examinations for Information Officers
- Final Provisions

Regulation Pertaining to the Association of Travel Agencies

Regulation Pertaining to the Association of Travel Agencies entered into effect on 4th September 1996. This Regulation was also prepared and put into effect in accordance with the Law concerning Travel Agencies and the Association of Travel Agencies, No: 1618. The Regulation contains the followings;

- Purpose and the Establishment
- Duties of the Association
- Bodies of the Association
- General Assembly
- Executive Board
- Inspection Council
- Disciplinary Council
- Revenue of the Association

The Regulation specifies in detail the aims, duties of the association; procedures and provisions concerning establishment, elections, meetings, and duties of its bodies as well as revenue of the association (<https://www.tursab.org.tr/regulations>).

3. TURSAB Rota B2B Online Platform

TURSAB designed a B2B marketing platform so as to facilitate the keeping the pace with the age of digital transformation within the context of travel agencies. Its structure is unique in the world in terms of being an online B2B sales platform of a professional association. So, it is a non-profit organisation. This platform, namely “Rota” (which means route in Turkish) recently went into action as a new business model of tourism industry in Turkey. “Rota” project arrived on the scene as a part of digital transformation program of TURSAB. The fundamental objective of Rota is to bring all TURSAB members together in an online package tour marketplace, to provide the interaction and to make contacts among these members.

The system of Rota is freely open to TURSAB members which serve as the online package tour marketplaces. Rota was constituted as the consequence of the negotiations realized with many regional chapters throughout Turkey. The generation of such a system is made up of the demands, expectations and contributions of TURSAB members of all regions in Turkey and the process of system development is still ongoing. For instance, a tea picking tour in Black Sea Region would easily reach to its fanciers throughout Turkey. These types of authentic tours would uplift the smaller scale travel agencies. The main objective is to create value added for tourism industry. Rota presents an easy, quick, and secure B2B tour sales platform to its members. In this platform, the members can realize the marketing and promotion of their tour products. Hence, Rota helps to the coverage of advertisement costs of travel agencies.

The business method is to inform the travel agencies in terms of the software and utilisation conditions specific to Rota, to provide the introduction of the internal package tours by increasing the active utilization of the system, to make the trade of such tours, and to administrate the business model thoroughly in order to manage the system properly. The members of Rota would reach to their target audience. Thus, they would benefit from a newly introduced business model of tourism in Turkey.

An integrated marketplace system, referred to variously as an integrated system or integrated portal, may comprise or communicate with modules for retail services, social networking, marketing information, ticketing sales, merchandise sales, membership services, or any other type and form of module (Boyd, 2013). Marketplace systems in the world are grown and developed by their users. The aim of Rota is accordingly in the same direction. In Rota platform, there are two fundamental role models as producer and the seller travel agency. Producer travel agencies will load their package tours to the system, and seller travel agencies will purchase the mentioned tours with the guarantee of Rota and TURSAB. Adjuratory members can undertake both roles at the same time. All the travel agencies organizing excursions and domestic package tours or the ones who would like to sell such kind of tours can join the system of Rota.

Turkey, as a tourism destination, encompasses a wide range of diversified package tour choices. There are numerous package tour types in the system of Rota from health to gastronomy, from educational to regional, from festivals to artistic attractions and natural adventure tours. The tours in Rota system are becoming diversified and they are getting more numerous day by day. Rota provides a secure travel shopping setting. It also presents authentic and regional tour alternatives with comparative programs and itineraries and special fares concerning to these tours through the supply generated by member travel agencies. This system considers the concern of consumers about having the service accurately and completely. In this context, Rota will resolve systematically the issues of cancellation and modification procedures about their payment, the issue of confidence in the case of defective

products. Thus and so, the consumers would plan their holiday programs confidentially through the guarantee of travel agencies association, namely TURSAB.

The main target of this project is to stimulate the consumers for making reservations of package tours via an official trustworthy system. TURSAB do not have any direct trade with the ultimate consumer due to the fact that Rota is a B2B trade platform. Customers can demand the tour programs from the travel agencies which are the member of Rota system. Furthermore, with the help of system integrations, travel agencies may integrate Rota and their web sites as well. By doing so, they will reach to the consumer directly and they will be able to realize online and confident trade.

Rota experienced a real short and an intensive preparation period of six months. Hence, it required a serious work and structuring. The process included a hard work of constituting online marketplace system, software phase, introducing the system to the travel agencies and trainings, determining the product categories, price analysis, quota utilization, forming the service criteria, preparing the legal contracts or agreements, integration of stakeholders into the system, and travel agency communication planning. This platform is designed in order for the utilization of travel agencies. Briefly the essential owners of the system are TURSAB member travel agencies. So, travel agencies are being and will be trained through the meetings organized by the Regional Chapters of TURSAB. These trainings provide the general information about the platform and the utilisation of the sub-contents of the platform.

The process of being a member of Rota is quite easy. Travel agencies which are TURSAB members may create an online membership application request in TURSAB Rota web site. Additionally, further information is presented in this web site. Same day, the requests are responded by emailing the unsigned agreements. Agreements signed by travel agencies are sent to TURSAB Rota. After being defined as the user, their passwords are sent. Eventually, they can start to use the system in the end of this facilitated online application process (TURSAB, 2020).

4. Content of Rota

There are nine sections in the platform. These are main page, sales, operation, reports, accounting, training, contacts, API (Application Programming Interface) and Favourites Pages (screenshots may be found in the appendix). In main page section there are announcements, daily, weekly and monthly performance, financial turnover according to the reservation types are listed.

Sales section is divided into two parts as tour sales and reservations. Tour sales sub-section presents the details of the tour such as price range, duration and excursion/séjour. Reservation sub-section includes the further information about sales type, departure and arrival date, name of the tour, owner of the reservation, option day etc.

Operations section is the most elaborated section which encompasses the sub-sections of composing the tour product, tour planning, tour quotas, cancellation of reservations, modification of reservations, cancellation of the tour, and picture manager.

Reports section specifies tour sales report, tour passengers list, payment details report, and cancellation report. Accounting section covers the invoice details. Education section offers some videos for the training of Rota platform. Contacts and favourite pages are formed in order to introduce the correspondences of the team and the useful links. API is optional for the members (TURSAB Rota Training Videos, 2020).

5. Integration of Rota Content to Members' Websites

Integration services for the web sites of ROTA member travel agencies have recently gone into operation. Agencies will have the opportunity to sell online TURSAB Rota tour products and packages respectively in their websites. This service is also free for the members. Member agencies may demand such integration easily. They may integrate the link sent by TURSAB Rota team to their own websites.

If demanded, XML (Extensible Markup Language) and Web API documentation may be reached by the member travel agencies which can produce specific solutions to their own web sites. Even for the ones which do not have a website, they may also sell online all of the tour products and packages in the platform through making use of TURSAB Rota product sales page. In order to have these types of website integrations, travel agencies should only write an e-mail to TURSAB Rota Operation Team.

One of the leading benefits of Rota is the facilitation of website integration. Simply put, especially in the online tourism industry, website integration is defined as the utilization of the technical infrastructure provided by another company and/or organization through sticking the label of your brand. White label and an API are two distinct solutions of integration. They serve to the similar aim. The main purpose of these solutions is the communication between the two platforms. In the focus of this study, the communication between overall Rota system and the website of the member travel agency.

Generally, white label travel website is an online booking portal that allows travel agents to sell hotels, flights, holidays, buses and other travel products to their customers simply and quickly. They can also manage all their financial transactions online and run numerous reports to aid the smooth running of their businesses. White label means there is no label. Members can use their own labels on the content. These websites can easily modify as per the need of the member. For white label solution members don't even need a technical team. Rota team does the work

for the members. Members control very little or don't control at all, the design and functionality of the product.

White label is a ready-made unbranded template that you can deploy on your website. It will link the member to the provider of certain services. So, the consumers will not necessarily quit the website of the member. In this case, they would have the access to the needed info in the website of the member. Additionally, members can tailor a white label to match their brands. By doing so, the customers will not consider that it's not a part of the member travel agency's website but a third-party template. An example of a travel white labelled product is a template solution by Expedia. It allows for adding the accommodation bookings to the member website.

Working in the back end, an API pulls out the requested data from external servers and displays it on the side of the member in its own way. This means that members design their own interface and use only the data of the Rota. Travelport, Amadeus and Flightstats are the major API examples on the travel market. Of two options, API involves a more sophisticated integration but at the same time, it's more adjustable. Prior to getting at it, the members should answer themselves whether they do need an API for this specific product.

6. Some API Practices of the Industry

Some extensively used practices in travel industry are presented in the following tables and figures. As a profit-oriented commercial private sector example, Technoheaven Company's functions and products are listed in Table 1. The further detailed services provided and added into the Figure 1. Ultimately, main travel industry APIs are introduced as a list in terms of their info and booking functions in Figure 2. The travel platform by Travelport facilitates travel commerce by connecting the world's leading travel providers with online and offline travel buyers in a proprietary business-to-business travel marketplace (Loureiro, 2017). Travelport's investments in unique airline merchandising capabilities, diverse hotel and car portfolio, innovative mobile and corporate travel technology and a pioneering payments solution positions it to service the world's rapidly growing demand. Innovative technology enables access to branded fares and ancillary products from hundreds of different airlines, hotel properties, car rental products and much more (Loureiro, 2016).

Table 1. Functions and Products of Technoheaven Company as An API Integration

Products	Functions
B2B – B2C Travel Portal	Hotel API Integrations
Travel Agency Software	Flight Integrations
Activity Booking Software	Tour API Integrations
Travel CRM	Payment Gateway Integrations
	Channel Manager

Source: <https://www.technoheaven.net/travel-software-development-company.aspx>

Figure 1. Detailed Services of Technoheaven Company

Source: <https://medium.com/@travelagencysoft/what-is-travel-technology-3abe00044da1>

Figure 2. Main Travel Industry APIs

Source: <https://www.traveldailymedia.com/travel-booking-apis/>

7. Conclusion

The “out of the gate” feature of Rota is its constitution on national tours. In this way, firstly the domestic tourism activities would come to a revival both with instant access and with an enormous diversification of tours. By doing so, brand new tour themes and itineraries would be developed and the relationships among the member travel agencies would be strengthened. Moreover, this digital software application would help to remove the informal or grey features of tourism economy. Because, all the transactions realized would be registered on an individual basis in such a platform. Other objectives are struggling against the illicit travel agency operations and avoiding unfair competition. This platform is a project of a non-profit organization of TURSAB.

Domestic tourism and local operations would be improved, and Rota would support the regional development by taking the invisible actors of tour production into consideration. Another aim is to extend the tourism activities to the whole year. No matter what the scale of the travel agency is, any travel agency of TURSAB may be the member of Rota. All sorts of travel agencies are involved. Rota offers a larger spectrum of production and sales for the member travel agencies. Therefore, brand new products of new diversifications and new tours in remote corners of Turkey may be on the scene of this online marketplace platform. The products can reach to the consumer by B2B2C channels. In other words, small sized travel agencies will have the opportunity to sell its unadvertised authentic tour via larger sized travel agencies. Secure sales, easy payment systems, instalment alternatives and package tour insurance are the advantages which may be used by member travel agencies.

Last but not the least, the team of Rota platform announced that their target is to create a contribution of five billion Turkish Liras to the package tour revenues in Turkey. In due course, Rota will not remain limited in domestic operations. The contents of the platform will be translated into five different languages. It will serve to international operations in near future.

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- <https://www.tursab.org.tr/regulations> Access Date: 18.06.2020

Appendix

The Screenshots of Main Contents (captured from Rota)

0 850 450 7682 (ROTA)

Ana Sayfa

Bildirimler

Acenta Entegrasyonlarımız Tüm Hızıyla Devam ediyor.
Değerli Acentalarımız,
Kısa dönem önce başlattığımız ve TURSAB ROTA sisteminde bulunan yurtiçi paket turların siz değerli Acentalarımızın web siteleri ü... [Devamını oku...](#)
28 Temmuz 2020

TURSAB ROTA Ticari düzenlemeler
TURSAB ROTA olarak Acentalarımızın yararına olacağını düşündüğümüz ticari düzenlemeleri hayata geçirdik.
Bu düzenlemeler ile amacımız Sat... [Devamını oku...](#)
19 Mayıs 2020

TURSAB ROTA ürünlerinin WEB Sitenize Entegrasyonu Hakkında
TURSAB ROTA tanımları ve Eğitim toplantılarında sistemimizin 2. Fazı olarak dile getirdiğimiz Acenta web sitesi

Günlük Performans

✓ Günlük + Haftalık + Aylık

Tamamlanmış tüm rezervasyonlar

Tamamlanmış ve konaklama gerçekleştirilmiş tüm rezervasyonlar

Tamamlanmış ve ileri kalkış tarihli tüm rezervasyonlar

0 850 450 7682 (ROTA)

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Tamamlanmış ve ileri kalkış tarihli tüm rezervasyonlar

TURSAB ROTA 0 850 450 7682 (ROTA) Yakin Ekin Akdeniz Univ

Ana Sayfa / Satış / Tur Satış

Tur Satış e? Ne Zaman? Ara

Rezervasyonlarım 93 tur bulundu. Siralama Popülerlik: En popüler önce

Kişi Başı Fiyat Aralığı 0TL 8.900TL

Tur Süresi 1Gün 14Gün

Ürün Tipi
 Günübirlik
 Konaklamalı

Kemaliye (Eğin) turu
Süre: 14 Saat 100,46 TL'den başlayan
✓ Kesin Hareket
GİDİLECEK YERLER: Kemaliye, Kemah, Erzincan Merkez / Erzincan Merkez
BAŞLANGIÇ / BİTİŞ: 7 ile 65 arası
YAŞ ARALIĞI: Günübirlik
KONAKLAMA: Otobüs, Midibüs, Minibüs
ULAŞIM: Şehir Gezisi
KATEGORİ: Utla Tur
DÜZENLEYEN: Utla Tur
01 Ağu 2020 10+ kaldı
02 Ağu 2020 10+ kaldı
08 Ağu 2020 10+ kaldı
09 Ağu 2020 10+ kaldı
Tur Broşürü Yazdır
Turu gör

Karavan Karadeniz Turu
Süre: 5 Gün 2.026,49 TL'den başlayan
GİDİLECEK YERLER: Trabzon Kalesi, Sümela Manastır, Kostaki Konağı (Trabzon Müzesi), Uzungöl, Köprübaşı / Trabzon, Rize Atatürk Evi Müzesi, Rize Merkez, Ayder Yaylası, Rize Müzesi
BAŞLANGIÇ / BİTİŞ: Trabzon Kalesi / Rize Kalesi
YAŞ ARALIĞI: 0 ile 90 arası
01 Ağu 2020 5 kaldı
08 Ağu 2020 5 kaldı
15 Ağu 2020 22 kaldı
22 Ağu 2020 5 kaldı

TURSAB ROTA 0 850 450 7682 (ROTA) Yakin Ekin Akdeniz Univ

Ana Sayfa / Satış / Rezervasyonlarım

Tur Satış Rezervasyonlarım

29.07.2020 Kalkış Tarih Aralığı

Voucher Tur Adı

Rezervasyon Sahibi İşlem Basamağı

Satış Tipi Ödeme Alınmış

Opsiyon Tarihi Kaynak

Ara Excele Aktar

Voucher	İptal Voucher	Satış Tipi	Satış Tarihi	Rezervasyon Sahibi	Tur Adı	Kalkış Tarihi	Opsiyon Tarihi	Satış Sorumlusu	Satış Acenta	Üretici Acenta	İşlem Basamağı	Kaynak	Oda / Kişi	Tutar	Ödenen Tutar	Sigorta Bedeli	Acenta Komisyon	Ödeme Sistemi Komisyonu	Kalan Tutar	Ödem Tipi
Kayıt bulunamadı.																				

0 850 450 7682 (ROTA) Yakın Ekin Akdeniz Üniversitesi

Ana Sayfa / Operasyon / Tur Planlama

Tur Planlama

Tur Bilgileri

Konaklama Türleri

Tur Kategorileri

Ulaşım Yöntemleri

Destinasyonlar

Tur Programı

Tur Resimleri

Dehil / Heriç Hizmetler

Fiyatlar ve Hareket

Turu Yayınla

Tur Adı

Konaklama Tipi

Süre Tipi

Fiyatlandırma Metodu

Bağlanç Destinasyon

Çocuk Dostu

Kısa Açıklama

İptal Koşulları

Otel Geceleme

Süre

Yaş Aralığı

Bitiş Destinasyon

Engelsiz Tatil

0 850 450 7682 (ROTA) Yakın Ekin Akdeniz Üniversitesi

Ana Sayfa / Raporlar / İptal Raporu

İptal Raporu

Satış Tarih Aralığı: 29.07.2020

İptal Tarih Aralığı:

Kalkış Tarih Aralığı:

Voucher:

Rezervasyon Sahibi:

Ara Excele Aktar

Voucher	İptal Voucher	Satış Tarihi	Satış Tipi	Rezervasyon Sahibi	Tur Adı	Kalkış Tarihi	Satış Sorumlusu	Satış Acenta	Üretici Acenta	Kaynak	Oda / Kişi	Tutar	Ödenen Tutar	Sigorta Bedeli	Acenta Komisyon	Ödeme Sistemi Komisyonu	Kalan Tutar	İptal Tarihi	İptal Eden Kullanıcı	İptal Tipi	İp Ar
Kayıt bulunamadı.																					

<https://portal.tursabrota.com/Report/TourPassengerList/Default.aspx>

The screenshot displays the 'Faturalar' (Invoices) section of the TURSAB ROTA web application. The interface is in Turkish and includes a navigation menu on the left with options like 'Ana Sayfa', 'Satış', 'Operasyon', 'Raporlar', 'Muhasebe', 'Eğitim', 'İletişim', 'API', and 'Favori Sayfalarım'. The main content area shows a search form for invoices with the following fields:

- Satış Tarih Aralığı: 29.07.2020
- Fatura Tarih Aralığı: (empty)
- İşlem Basamağı: Final
- Yazdırıldı: -
- Kalkış Tarih Aralığı: (empty)
- Fatura Tipi: (dropdown)
- Satış Tipi: (dropdown)
- Fatura Ünvan: (text input)
- Kaynak: (dropdown)

Buttons for 'Ara' (Search) and 'Excel Aktar' (Export to Excel) are located at the bottom right of the form. Below the form is a table with the following columns: #, Fatura ID, Voucher, Fatura Tipi, Fatura Acenta, Fatura Muhatap Acenta, Rezervasyon Sahibi, Rezervasyon Tarihi, Satış Tipi, İşlem Basamağı, Satış Acenta, Üretici Acenta, Kaynak, Tur Tarihi, Ünvan, Adres, TC Kimlik No, Vergi Dairesi, Vergi No, Fatura Tarihi, Fatura No. The table is currently empty, with the text 'Kayıt bulunamadı.' (No records found) displayed below the header.

The browser address bar shows the URL: <https://portal.tursabrota.com/Finance/Invoice/Default.aspx#dropdown-M16>. The system tray at the bottom right indicates the date and time: TR, 15:00, 29.07.2020.